

Big Data Analytics on Spark and Hadoop and on AWS Cloud

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

Performing Big Data Analytics on 100s of TBs or PBs is a very expensive undertaking, if it is performed on an on-prem Hadoop cluster involving dozens of servers. The bill for such a set up can run few million dollars each year. I have lived through such systems. Talk with focus on a recently completed cost-effective and scalable data analytics in the AWS cloud, with EMR, Spark, Athena and Redshift, that was developed with a very small fraction of the cost of similar on-prem solutions.

2. Aim

To highlight the benefits of scalable and elastic big data computation on the cloud, where you separate the compute (AWS EMR,) from the storage (S3,) and operate with a small fraction of cost and plus with additional benefit of with many other big data tools like Athena, Redshift, Elastic Search and Graph Databases and AI systems.

Every modern big data app, has elements of batch, real time streaming and machine learning. The audience will get an understanding of what it takes to build such an application, with Spark and other Big Data tools on AWS Cloud and with live coding and demos.

3. Material and methods

We effectively separated storage on S3, from the computation on Spark and AWS Elastic Map Reduce Hadoop cluster, and ran a batch and streaming ETL, on 100 TB i.e. 10 years of orders and trades, on EMR cluster of 10 – 40 nodes. Now that the final results are stored as 250 column wide tables and as 45 TB of compressed and partitioned parquet datasets on S3, the Analytics can take many facets

Athena, a serverless computer on AWS Cloud is based on presto. It gives power of 100 node Hadoop cluster. What is so outstanding is our typical query running on the entire dataset of 100 TB, return the result under 45 seconds. Such a performance was unheard of few years ago. And it's a surprising an analytical query on 100 TB only cost 20 cents on AWS AthenaFor a more advanced analysis, we run the Scala compiled apps on Spark SQL, Spark Graph Frames and Spark ML pipelines. Zeppelin and Jupiter Hub on AWS EMR cluster, runs our interactive analysis on 100 TB datasets Redshift and Redshift Spectrum on S3, analyze data and join the datasets with the rest of DWH tables

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4. Results

The results are obtained through running the Data and Advanced analytics on each of the above

Optimized and partitioned 45 parquet on TB 250 Columns Data sets, 50 Billion Rows

Table 1:

	Select count(*) from table	Select c1, c2, sum(c3) from table group by c1, c2	Cube, Rollup and WindowFrames	Cost
AWS Athena	26 Secs	33 Secs		Cost Per Query \$0.20
AWS Redshift Spectrum cluster with 5 nodes	8 Secs	4 Secs		
Spark SQL on 20 Node AWS EMR Cluster	7 Mins	13 Mins	18 Mins, 15 sec	Cost Per Hour \$45.00

In edition, we run spark machine learning pipelines and graph analysis with graph frames on EMR (10 node to 30 nodes) from time to time pay as you go model , but they are brought up for few hours in a day.

The above is one such result table, in addition, I have many others which take you through the Classical Regression followed by ML pipelines and then Deep Learning on Apache Spark that evaluate the performance and accuracy of the solutions for the same dataset. The accuracy run from 68 percent with the Basic Naïve Bayes 79 percent with Regression with pipelines and parameter grid and 97.5 with Deep Learning.

5. Conclusions

The total onetime cost of ETL and Spark Streaming to transfer 60 TB of order and trades resulting in partitioned dataset on S3, \$15,000. The net cost of running analytics for such a system is about 25K per year instead of 800K per year

AWS Athena and Redshift provide a power of 100 node Hadoop cluster but only cost a fraction. This may be the only platform that will emerge out of a maze of big data platforms.

6. Keywords

Big Data, Hadoop, AWS Cloud, AWS Athena, Apache Spark, Spark ML Pipelines, Spark GraphFrames, Deep Learning, Redshift, Redshift Spectrum, AWS S3, AWS EMR,

Deep Learning

References

Author biography

Robert Sachar is a Cloud Architect and Software Engineer with Millennium Partners LLC. Prior to this I worked at Credit Suisse and investment bank based in NY on Big data and Hadoop for 19 year and I was the head of the department of Big Data and client innovation solutions. I hold a Masters Degree in Computer Sciences from Rutgers University, NJ

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